

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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IMPACT OF ELECTRONIC HEALTH RECORDS DOCUMENTATION AND
CLINICAL DOCUMENTATION SPECIALISTS ON CASE MIX INDEX:
A RETROSPECTIVE STUDY FOR QUALITY IMPROVEMENT

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

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ABSTRACT

The implementation of hospital electronic health records software is considered a significant modernization in healthcare. The objective of this study was to evaluate the impact of electronic health records and the addition of clinical documentation specialists as a clinical support group on hospitalist documentation using case mix index (CMI) as a measurement tool. A two-group pre/postimplementation retrospective research design was used to evaluate the impact of electronic health records and clinical documentation specialists on CMI in a single 125-bed full-service community hospital in the greater Los Angeles area. All hospitalist medical records were reviewed in the pre/postphases. A total of 3,536 records were reviewed over the two phases. Phase one included a review of 1,712 hospitalist medical records before implementation of electronic health records. Phase two included a review of 1,824 hospitalist medical records after implementation of electronic health records and clinical documentation specialists. Change in CMI data were analyzed over the two phases. CMI data were treated as interval data and analyzed by parametric descriptive statistics in two phases by one-way ANOVA to compare the means between the two phases. The mean CMI value for phase one was 1.65 and 1.68 for phase two. One-way ANOVA yielded no difference between the mean CMI values for the two phases ($p = .53$). The implementation of electronic health records and clinical documentation specialists as a clinical support group did not make any significant difference in hospitalist documentation using CMI as a measurement tool.

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BACKGROUND

The American Recovery and Reinvestment Act of 2009 was enacted to promote the adoption and use of electronic health records (EHRs) through stages of meaningful use. The adoption of EHRs by providers and hospitals as mandated by the Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS) have brought about concerns regarding the impact to quality of care and provider documentation. Unfortunately, little research is available to help guide the adoption of EHRs in the hospital setting while preserving the quality of EHRs provider documentation of Medicare Severity-Diagnosis Related Groups (MS-DRGs) and quality of care. In fact, recent research is unavailable to establish a specific measurement variable that provides agencies with an evaluation mechanism to monitor provider documentation of MS-DRGs diagnosis after adoption of EHRs. However, case mix index (CMI) is a well-known standard in hospital administration and operations that reflects a relative value assigned to MS-DRGs diagnoses that is used to determine the allocation of resources to care for, treat, and determine the quality of provider documentation of MS-DRGs diagnoses. Most importantly, accurate and comprehensive documentation of MS-DRGs diagnosis with appropriate and accurate addition of comorbidities improves the representation of an institution's delivery of quality of care by estimating accurate expected and observed mortality. With the addition of observed comorbidities to the MS-DRGs diagnoses, the expected mortality rate appropriately increases without affecting the observed mortality rate (Spellberg et al., 2013). This is extremely important when institutions report mandatory mortality rates to regulatory agencies for assessment of quality. Those institutions that have poor documentation of MS-DRGs diagnosis that does not reflect comorbid states can appear to

have poor quality of care related to comparisons of expected and observed mortality rates that may or may not be accurate related to documentation alone. An added benefit of accurate and comprehensive documentation of MS-DRGs diagnosis is the reimbursement associated with higher weighted MS-DRGs.

The purpose of provider documentation is to establish diagnoses, evaluate progress, and record evidence of care that is, in turn, used to measure quality of care via mortality and morbidity statistics and finally adjudication for payment of the care delivered. The use of MS-DRGs is the standard for monitoring, evaluating, and payment of care delivered. Therefore, the importance of accurate and comprehensive provider documentation is imperative to accurately represent the severity of illness of a patient in order to establish appropriate care delivered. Measurement of CMI takes these variables into account and therefore can be utilized as a measuring tool for severity of illness and expected mortality rates.

Several recent studies have shown the impact of appropriate documentation of MS-DRGs and comorbidities. Kumar and Thomas (2011) performed a study to evaluate and explore various means by which clinicians and healthcare information management staff members missed potential technical fee reimbursement due to poor documentation or lack of knowledge of the newer MS-DRGs coding system. Although the study's sample size was low, the impact of their findings was impressive. The study analyzed five randomly selected inpatient medical records for accuracy and comprehensive diagnoses which included comorbidities. They found that by correctly understanding the newer MS-DRGs coding specifications and documenting patient diagnoses and comorbidities to appropriate reimbursement levels, the hospital increased its payments by

about \$50,000. They concluded that by educating clinicians and health information management staff members to be rigorous in the interpretation of patients' MS-DRGs diagnosis, comorbidities, and treatment protocol, the hospital could reclaim potentially millions of dollars annually (Kumar & Thomas, 2011). The complex nature of the MS-DRGs system is further compromised by the addition of mandated and complex computerized EHRs systems that are expected to ultimately represent the model for care delivery and payment.

The new MS-DRGs standard of documenting and coding diagnoses has profound documentation and coding implications for hospitals and providers. The new payment system is one of several new value-based care initiatives that CMS designed to influence patient care in acute care hospitals and provider reimbursement by rewarding hospitals that yield best-practice outcomes and penalizing those that do not (Rosenstein, O'Daniel, White, & Taylor, 2009). Utilizing the new MS-DRGs system, CMS operates a substantial hospital- and provider-populated data system to analyze and measure clinical performance and best-practice care outcomes. These guidelines are applied to reward-and-penalty systems to guide reimbursement. Therefore, it has become increasingly imperative that providers document all diagnoses and comorbid conditions that are present on admission and occur during hospitalization. The omission of any diagnosis that may be interpreted as a hospital-acquired condition will not be reimbursed and will be counted against the hospital in terms of quality and mortality statistics. An important characteristic of the new MS-DRGs system is that any hospital-acquired complication is the financial responsibility of the hospital and not reimbursed by payers using MS-DRGs as a payment system.

The principal diagnosis is a predetermined diagnosis that is dictated by CMS through historical study data that increase the cost of care by requiring increased hospital resources to treat patients. Documentation of the severity of illness is performed by the addition of comorbid conditions classified as major comorbidities and complications (MCC) and comorbidities and complications (CC). MCC and CC are conditions or complications that complicate the treatment of the principal diagnosis by demanding higher resources to manage the patient. The addition of comorbidities also affects the representation of quality of care provided by appropriately adjusting observed and expected mortality rates that accurately characterize the risk of a patient. Also, comprehensive provider documentation provides justification for the medical necessity of the admission and resources required to care for patients.

CMI can be utilized by hospital and administrative staff to measure and predict reimbursement, quality of care, and quality of provider documentation of MS-DRGs diagnosis. CMI is highly dependent on provider documentation and coding of MS-DRGs with the addition of MCC and CC. However, caution should be observed when using CMI to accurately predict severity of illness of an institution without first evaluating the quality of provider documentation. Classifying institutions as a poor quality facility has severe consequences to the physicians and staff. Determining the quality of documentation of a facility prior to classification can help determine the accuracy of such classification (Mendez, Harrington, Christenson, & Spellberg, 2014).

Problem Statement

Comprehensive and accurate provider documentation represents delivery of quality hospital patient care and financial state as measured by CMI. However, recent

research shows that provider documentation compliance is difficult to achieve despite quality methodologies and study designs using traditional paper populated charts (Spurgeon, Hiser, & Litofsky, 2011). Moreover, with the adoption of mandated EHRs, failure of providers to perform accurate and comprehensive documentation has negative quality and financial impact potential for providers and hospitals (Didier, Pace, & Walker, 2008). Recent mandates from CMS to adopt EHRs in hospital and provider practices have complicated hospital initiatives to improve clinical provider documentation campaigns (Rosenstein et al., 2009). Furthermore, healthcare delivery organizations, specifically acute care hospitals, have considerable interest in the success of their providers to comply with documentation regulations for financial and quality success. Hospital Inpatient Quality Reporting mandates reporting quality measures to CMS as part of Medicare Prescription Drug, Improvement, and Modernization Act of 2003 Section 501(b). Hospitals that fail to report quality measures are penalized up to 2% in annual payment rates. In addition, the Deficit Reduction Act of 2005 supports penalties with expectations that the reduction in payment could rise under the Affordable Care Act in or around 2014-2015. Public knowledge of provider and hospital quality mortality statistics and utilization is reported by CMS to the public for review on the Hospital Compare website at www.hospitalcompare.hhs.gov ("With Public Reporting on the Rise," 2008). Currently, hospital organizations struggle with provider compliance to comprehensively document diagnoses that reflect accurate MS-DRGs with accompanied MCC/CC (Rosenstein et al., 2009). The adoption of mandated complex EHRs systems offers a considerable concern for hospitals that struggle with provider documentation compliance because providers tend to concentrate on maneuvering through the

components of EHRs rather than accurate and comprehensive documentation (Kargul, Wright, Knight, McNichol, & Riggio, 2013). EHRs adoption is a large endeavor by hospitals both financially and logistically. Hospitals are at significant risk of losing revenue and quality ratings if providers are not committed to the success of the adoption, as documentation quality will significantly decrease related to EHRs documentation time restraints placed on providers. Unlike hospitals, providers are compensated by visit evaluation and management codes that are set by CMS and do not currently change based on quality of care provided. The incentive to perform documentation that requires more time is understandably not met with much enthusiasm and dedication by the providers. Most importantly, MS-DRGs data are collected by CMS and other federal agencies for analysis of disease states, predictions for future reimbursement schedules, and epidemiological research. Inaccurate provider documentation of MS-DRGs diagnosis ultimately places matters of public health at risk by misrepresenting the data in which agencies make health policy decisions.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this project was to evaluate the impact of implementation of EHRs and clinical documentation specialists (CDSs) as a clinical support team on provider documentation of MS-DRGs and MCC/CC as measured by CMI.

SUPPORTING FRAMEWORK

The Iowa model was chosen as a conceptual framework for evidence-based practice to promote quality of care (Titler et al., 2001). The conceptual model utilizes seven steps to implement a problem or knowledge focused trigger from identification to implementation of an evidence-based practice resolution to promote quality care. The seven steps of the model are as follows: selection of the topic, forming a team, evidence retrieval, grading the evidence, developing evidence-based practice standard, implement the evidence-based practice, and evaluation. The model steps helped guide the project organization.

Selection of a Topic

The adoption of EHRs into a hospital organization is a multidisciplinary project that affects all areas of practice by temporarily disrupting clinical, nursing, and physician flow. The selection of this topic was driven by planned adoption of EHRs as a tool to accent our current benchmark of documentation throughout the hospital organization and to comply with meaningful use mandates. Moreover, accurate and comprehensive provider documentation of MS-DRGs establishes patients' severity of illness which ultimately maintains an accurate hospital record of quality of care that then can be reported to federal, state, and local regulatory agencies for hospital quality ratings.

Forming a Team

Team members were chosen using a bottom-up approach that included staff from all areas of the hospital organization. The members included those employees who participated in direct and indirect patient care. Prior to implementation of EHRs, a team of interested stakeholders were chosen that included physicians, nurse practitioners,

pharmacists, staff nurses, administrative personnel, coders, information technology (IT) personnel, and other multidisciplinary team members. During the development stage the team used evidence from an extensive literature search that would help successfully promote the implementation of EHRs by engaging stakeholders and ensure continuation of excellent provider documentation.

In addition to hospital employees, we introduced CDSs as an adjunct clinical support team for providers to ensure continuation of current documentation practices during the implementation of the EHRs system. CDSs are trained document specialists with advanced degrees in medicine. Specific to this project, we employed two physicians who had extensive training in documentation. Their specific training beyond a medical degree included DRGs, MS-DRGs, and identification of comorbidities that enhance accurate and comprehensive provider documentation. The CDSs' knowledge base of major complications and comorbidities helps the hospitalist provider document accurate and comprehensive medical records, thereby increasing the weight of MS-DRGs and ultimately increasing CMI. Their input into the project was to evaluate concurrent hospitalist charts and suggest diagnoses that may have been missed by the hospitalist so that a complete and accurate medical record could then be billed for adjudication. CDSs personnel are not licensed physicians in the United States, so their suggestions were limited to official coding queries that were submitted for final review by the hospitalist provider before entered as part of an official medical record.

Two physician champions were chosen by the medical staff to promote physician involvement and to achieve buy-in for EHRs and CDSs. Singling out physician champions to promote buy-in was prompted mainly by preliminary results from the

Minimizing Error, Maximizing Outcome (MEMO) study performed in 2013. The study looked at physicians' stress and burnout when asked to convert from paper charting to electronic medical record documentation. Introducing physicians to complex and new electronic medical record systems significantly increased stress and burnout. Allowing physicians to be involved in the planning stages reduced stress and burnout (Babbott et al., 2014). In addition to the chosen team of stakeholders and end users, a special question and answer panel with the medical staff was conducted to get physicians on board with clinical documentation and EHRs implementation. Leaders from the medical staff spoke about meaningful use and the governmental purpose of establishing EHRs (Didier et al, 2008). A real-time demonstration of the impact of accurate documentation of MS-DRGs was performed during the meeting by randomly pulling 10 medical records and comprehensively recoding them. Similar to the study performed by Kumar and Thomas (2011), we were able to demonstrate to the medical staff an increase in revenue of \$36,000 and an increase in expected mortality rate.

Evidence Retrieval/Literature Review

The goal for the literature review was to acquire specific evidence that would assist in the steps for successful implementation of EHRs and provide sound evidentiary support to establish the importance of accurate and comprehensive documentation of MS-DRGs so that the level of care provided is clearly evident in the medical record. In addition, we searched for any literature that could measure accurate and comprehensive documentation of MS-DRGs. The comprehensive multidisciplinary team members met during several sessions to structure search guidelines for evidence to guide both the implementation of EHRs and to support continued excellence in provider MS-DRGs

documentation. A literature search utilized multiple databases such as CINAHL, MEDLINE, Cochran, Google Scholar, and Pub Med to acquire recent evidence to support our goal to implement EHRs while maintaining clinical documentation excellence. The search was limited to literature from 2009 to present. We used the following keywords in each search engine and database: *medical severity diagnosis related groups, diagnosis related groups, provider documentation, electronic medical records, electronic health records, and electronic health records and case mix index.*

We found several studies that support accurate and comprehensive provider documentation of MCC and CC to increase reimbursement and represent the quality of care delivered. However, we did not find any studies that evaluated if EHRs systems improve provider documentation as represented by a stable or increased CMI. We did find enough evidence to support phases of implementation of a project that will prepare our hospital for 100% adoption of EHRs while maintaining our quality of care and financial health through continued excellence in clinical documentation as measured by CMI. We were unable to find any directly related research available that fit the research question that guided our search. We included studies that developed strategies for successful EHRs adoption in the hospital setting and examined the importance of provider documentation of MS-DRGs that specifically relates to quality of care and the financial impact of provider documentation. We excluded studies that were not relevant to our practice setting such as ambulatory medicine and outpatient clinics except for one study that concentrated on strategies for the adoption of EHRs (Paterson et al., 2010). The studies that were included afforded successful strategies for the implementation of EHRs and the importance of provider documentation.

The institution of EHRs in hospitals and the advent of MS-DRGs are relatively new requirements of CMS; hence, limited research is available on the topic. Jha et al. (2009) illustrates that less than 2% of U.S. hospitals have a comprehensive EHRs system in use. The American Recovery and Reinvestment Act of 2009 states that U.S. health policy is aiming for 100% adoption of a comprehensive EHRs system by 2015. The Institute of Medicine developed a list of functionalities that are needed to qualify as a comprehensive inpatient EHRs. In order to qualify as a comprehensive EHRs system, hospitals must incorporate physician and nursing components that include clinical documentation, test and imaging results, computerized provider-order entry, and decision support tools. They found that several barriers to implementation of comprehensive EHRs systems included capital budget for the cost of adequate systems, financial incentives, technical support staff cost, and limited interest in stakeholders. Although this study illustrates that U.S. hospitals are lagging behind the goals of the federal government, intense hospital industry competitiveness is forcing organizations to adopt systems and implement them in order to meet meaningful use requirements (Jha et al., 2009). This 2009 study was indeed relevant at the time; however, it does not represent the current rapid adoption of EHRs systems in use since the 5 years the study was performed.

On February 17, 2012, a news release from the Department of Health and Human Services announced major progress in hospital use of health IT. According to the survey, 2000 hospitals and 41,000 doctors have received \$3.1 billion in payments for ensuring meaningful use of EHRs systems. U.S. hospital adoption of EHRs systems have doubled from 16% to 35% between 2009 and 2011.

Paterson et al. (2010) offered a strong framework to guide the successful implementation of the EHRs system. The researchers evaluated common barriers to successful implementation of EHRs systems. The qualitative study produced a conceptual model for successful implementation of EHRs systems by highlighting important factors that promote participation of the stakeholders and users of the systems. Prior to implementation of our project, we followed the steps offered in this study to inspire a successful implementation of both the EHRs system and documentation guidelines. The 11 steps will be discussed later. To date, the value of Paterson et al.'s suggestion is considered invaluable.

Kumar and Thomas (2011) performed a pilot study of five random charts to concurrently review if documentation lacked applicable MCC and CC diagnosis. After review of the charts, they found that adding appropriate complications and comorbid states increased reimbursement to the hospital by \$47,766 for the five reviewed charts (Kumar & Thomas, 2011).

Spurgeon et al. (2011) performed a three-phase quality improvement project to promote improved provider documentation in order to more accurately represent International Classification of Diseases, Ninth Revision (ICD-9), coding and capture severity of illness risk of mortality which, in turn, leads to appropriate reimbursement to the hospital while accurately representing quality. They used similar intervention strategies to our project with paper charting. The researchers implemented group in-service on progress notes templates and concurrent medical record coder review to enhance capture of diagnoses that increased severity of illness. They expected to see a difference after the intervention with an increase in severity of illness. However, they

were not able to establish a statistically significant difference secondary to very poor compliance of the physicians, 45% response rate (Spurgeon et al., 2011).

Rosenstein et al. (2009) confirmed the financial impact of DRGs to MS-DRGs conversion and the importance of physician documentation of MCC and CC. A large data mapping design to assess and project individual hospital and aggregate results after conversion to MS-DRGs was performed utilizing 66,000 cases over 53 hospitals. They converted 10 top DRGs to MS-DRGs and found that using the DRGs system the hospital lost \$10 million. After conversion to MS-DRGs, with the addition of MCC and CC, the hospital gained \$12 million. The study also suggested a nine-step process and guidelines to succeed at physician documentation (Rosenstein et al., 2009).

Kargul et al. (2013) performed a retrospective study of 220 charts that implemented a hybrid EHRs progress notes to enhance provider documentation of principal diagnosis, MCC and CC. In our design of our progress notes, we utilized the study's findings by including automatic population of labs, vital signs, and the history and physical component of the history of present illness. According to the study, the population of these variables allows the provider to concentrate on documentation of principal diagnosis, MCC and CC (Kargul et al., 2013).

Galanter, Hier, Jao, and Sarne (2010) utilized an EHRs system that incorporates a clinical decision support intervention that alerted the provider while placing in orders electronically to add to or modify the problem list that ultimately adds to MCC and CC documentation. Although the study limitations were forthcoming with the problem of poor physician compliance, they were able to improve the problem list 75% of the time. During the design of the progress notes, the researchers set hard-level alert pop-ups to

alert the provider that a certain diagnosis should be considered based on radiological and laboratory data that was populated in the system. Alert validity was 96% with a false rate of 5%. Ninety-five percent of the alerts made to the diagnosis yielded a 95% accuracy rate as determined by an independent reviewer (Galanter et al., 2010).

Mendez et al. (2014) evaluated CMI as an indicator for financial payment to hospitals and its utilization as an indicator for severity of illness. The authors noted that CMI is dependent on coding and provider documentation. In addition, they found that accurate CMI in the public sector is different than in the private sector secondary to financial resources available for provider documentation education (Mendez et al., 2014).

Most importantly, we were able to find numerous recent studies that showed that simple educational intervention has significant impact on documentation accuracy quality metrics and revenue generation. Zalatimo, Ranasinghe, Harbaugh, and Iantosca (2014) performed a pre and posteducational implementation study that noted significant improvement in All Patient Refined Diagnosis Related Groups (APR-DRGs) weight, CMI, and revenue margin improvement. An APR-DRGs weight increased from $2.123 \pm .1402$ to $2.514 \pm .224$. The severity of index increased from $1.863 \pm .0855$ to $2.154 \pm .130$. CMI increased from 2.429 ± 0.153 to 2.825 ± 0.232 . A 42.2% average margin per discharge increase was also noted (Zalatimo et al., 2014).

Spellberg et al. (2013) showed that specific and accurate documentation of patient diagnosis comorbidities in the medical record is critical to drive quality improvement and to ensure accuracy of publicly reported data. As with Zalatimo et al. (2014), both studies were performed at an academic tertiary center. Spellberg et al. found that after an educational program of internal medicine residents, the median quarterly complication

codes and major complication codes capture rate increased from 42% to 48% ($p = .003$). Observed mortality did not change, but the expected mortality increased, resulting in a 30% decline in median quarterly mortality index ($p = .001$). In addition, median quarterly CMI increased from 1.27 to 1.36 ($p = .004$). The study findings are practically significant; however, the authors made several basic errors in the analysis of the data presented. In comparing CMI in the pre/postintervention stages, they treated CMI data as ordinal; in fact, it is interval. Hence, using the nonparametric Mann-Whitney U test to find a significant difference is misleading and inappropriate. However, this alone does not change the importance and clinical significance of the educational program that they developed and performed. Spellberg et al. were able to yield an increase in CMI through the educational program.

Barnes, Waterman, MacIntyre, Coughenour, and Kessel (2010) related increased quality documentation to an increase in hospital net income. In this study, the authors used a standardized documentation template for evaluation and management of progress notes that focused on accuracy and efficiency of resident documentation. CMI, reimbursement rate, payer distribution, hospital charges, costs, and payments were compared before and after implementation of standardized template progress notes. They found a 24% increase in the hospital's net income for trauma care, constituting \$1.45 million increase, although a 12% decrease in patient volume was noted during the observation period. In addition, admission profitability increased by 42%. Increases in both injury severity score and CMI were seen ($p < .05$) after recommendation of the program. They concluded that a standardized documentation strategy resulted in significant fiscal gains in hospital reimbursement (Barnes et al., 2010).

Grading the Evidence

All the studies were quantitative studies that were utilized to develop an understanding of implementation of the EHRs process based on evidence as well as the importance of provider documentation of MS-DRGs to yield quality of care and positive financial impact. All of the studies were level 2 retrospective or retrospective cohorts. One study was a correlation study. A table of evidence (see Appendix A) provides a detailed list of the key research articles discussed.

DEVELOPING AN EVIDENCE-BASED PRACTICE STANDARD/METHODS

Study Design

A retrospective study of CMI 1 year prior and 1 year after the implementation was performed in two phases. CMI for all hospitalist patients were collected from hospital financial software. Baseline CMI was calculated for this time period. Phase two of the study, the implementation phase, was performed in the implementation period. We noted 100% compliance with EHRs documentation for all encounters from each hospitalist provider during the implementation phase. Institutional Review Board approval was obtained from the hospital's ethical review board.

Implementing Evidence-Based Practice/Selection of Participants

The project took place in a Los Angeles, California, full-service community hospital with a 24-hour emergency service. Medicare and private-sector insurance make up the primary source of payers. Several key personnel were identified prior to the implementation phase. Hospitalist, CDSs, coders, and IT technicians were educated to the study design and purpose.

Hospitalist providers are contracted with the hospital to perform inpatient services. Hospitalists are specially trained providers, either medical doctors or nurse practitioners, trained in the specialties of pulmonary critical care or internal medicine. Their training beyond their medical discipline integrates aspects of hospital care into their practice. Common characteristics of a hospitalist practice include expert knowledge in hospital economics, understanding length of stay compared to geometric length of stay, diagnosis-related groups, and documentation. Hospitalists maintain a clear understanding

of rigorous requirements that payers such as Medicare and Medicaid require to obtain accurate reimbursement, such as evaluation and management criteria.

CDSs were utilized as an adjunct to EHRs in order to assist the providers in identifying MCC and CC diagnosis. Their responsibilities as expert MS-DRGs documentation specialists were to liaison between the coders and providers to help facilitate and educate providers on concurrent medical records that were missing relevant diagnoses that were evident in the medical record data.

Certified coders are hospital employees responsible for evaluating the medical records for accurate and comprehensive representation of the principal diagnosis, MCC, and CC before billing payers. Coders are charged with providing accurate records of billing to the payers. In our organization, they assume the de facto role of billing and documentation compliance officers. They verify that the diagnoses are supported by valid, objective, and accurate data populated in the medical record.

IT was the largest group of personnel utilized in our project. The team was made up of experienced IT members with many years of education and experience in hospital information systems. The technical component was enriched by the addition of registered nurse and physician informatics specialists who were added to the team of IT personnel in order to ensure clinician input in the design of the system. The IT team, with the assistance of the clinician informatics personnel, implemented the hardware and software and developed the progress notes and history and physical templates for the EHRs system used in our project.

Project leaders adopted 11 factors for EHRs implementation success, which are outlined in Keshavjee's factors for EHRs implementation success: governance, project

leadership, involving stakeholders, selling benefits, technology usability, early planning, implementation assistance, training, feedback and dialogue, support, and user groups (Paterson et al., 2010). Phase one started 6 months prior to implementation of EHRs by forming a planning committee of key stakeholders from each patient care department. The committee included interested stakeholders from each hospital division that were considered end-users. End-users were defined as departments that were involved in direct and indirect patient care. The members of the team were specialists in particular areas who supported the project. The members of the team included CDSs, hospital administrators, internal medicine physicians, an acute care nurse practitioner, IT specialists, Meditech® support staff, registered nurses, and professional medical coders who made up the clinical support team.

The team reviewed the latest available research literature to implement the best evidence-supported practice for EHRs implementation strategies, including MS-DRGs documentation importance to quality and hospital finance and MS-DRGs documentation as it impacts CMI. We discovered that one of the key elements for success for EHRs implementation was to identify positive elements for each group to achieve buy-in. The groups were allowed and encouraged to make important decisions on the implementation and construction of the components of EHRs which proved to be essential to implementation success. The process also encouraged identification of leaders and champions who showed interest in the project. Several interested medical staff members were chosen to develop and build progress notes with the IT and Meditech® teams. The final progress notes built incorporated several timesaving features that were presented to the medical staff by the medical staff champions. Automatic and up-to-date data

population of laboratory data, vital signs, and parts of the history of present illness were designed to prepopulate data to subsequent notes. The medical staff voted in favor of the progress notes, thereby assisting in buy-in. After 6 months of weekly meetings and strict adherence to the steps for successful implementation, a milieu of acceptance formed and engagement in training followed. Providers, nurses, pharmacists, and clerical staff were trained by IT support staff and Meditech® support staff with *dummy patients*. Several months of training and proficiency evaluations followed for each group of end-users. One of the most important decisions the committee made was to allow for the availability of the support staff to provide one-on-one training 24/7 for all participants who needed it. All stakeholders were given the opportunity to pick a start date, which was followed by the administration. The implementation of the EHRs system started on the agreed-upon date. Computerized provider order entry was delayed 6 months to allow time for the providers to familiarize themselves with the documentation modules of EHRs.

Phase one of the study consisted of preparation for EHRs and CDSs implementation and retrospective analysis of CMI 1 year prior to phase two, the implementation phase. After successful buy-in from the stakeholders, the implementation phase was successfully started. Directives from administration forced 100% compliance for the use of EHRs progress notes and history and physicals for patient documentation by all hospitalist providers. Hospitalist providers were prohibited from using paper chart progress notes in patient care areas by the medical director and administration to ensure compliance by the hospitalist providers. IT and support staff were available in all patient care areas 24 hours a day and 7 days a week. IT and support

staff performed daily reports detailing compliance, complaints, and interventions to help providers achieve 100% compliance.

CDSs personnel started performing real-time chart reviews and daily rounds 1 day after the start date. CDSs staff assisted the hospitalist providers in identifying possible documentation deficits by reviewing possible MCC/CC diagnoses that were present in the medical record. Formal queries were generated and presented to the hospitalist for review and placement of addendums in EHRs on a daily basis. Appropriate addendums were performed by the hospitalist when appropriate.

Data Analysis

Analysis was performed in two phases. The first phase of the analysis was performed prior to implementation of EHRs and CDSs. CMI for all hospitalist patients were collected from the hospital financial software and a baseline CMI was calculated for the time period prior to implementation of EHRs. Ongoing evaluation noted 100% compliance with EHRs documentation for all encounters from each hospitalist provider during the implementation phase. Both phases of data collection were of the same data format. The second phase of the analysis was performed after implementation of EHRs and CDSs. Data for each phase were extracted from the hospital financial software into separate Microsoft Excel spreadsheets. The data were cleaned by deleting records with blank CMI values ($n = 26$). The spreadsheets were then combined into a single file, and a grouping variable was created to designate the phase from which the data originated. The final data file was then imported into the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS v. 21) for analysis.

All study data were extracted from the hospital financial software package using the exact search criteria for each phase of the study. Search criteria were all patients on the hospitalist service during the time period specified, the number of MS-DRGs, weights for each MS-DRGs, hospital blended rate (provided by CMS), and CMI. After analysis of CMI was performed, post hoc and A Priori power analysis were performed to assist in future study preparation.

Subgroup Analysis Methods

CMI were evaluated for five subgroups that historically show a large difference in weights when MCC and CC are appropriately applied. The detailed analysis looked at CMI across phases, looking at a more limited subgroup of MS-DRGs. Five MS-DRGs codes were selected from the overall data, and mean CMI values were calculated for each study phase. The five MS-DRGs codes were: 870 (Sepsis with mechanical ventilation 96 hours or greater), 871 (Sepsis without mechanical ventilation for 96 hours or greater with MCC), 872 (Sepsis without mechanical ventilation for 96 hours or greater without MCC), 682 (Acute Renal Failure with CC/MCC), and 684 (Acute Renal Failure without CC/MCC).

Evaluation

Project evaluation was continuous throughout phase one and phase two. The evaluation process was centered and guided by the purpose of the study. In short, do EHRs impact hospitalist provider documentation of MS-DRGs as measured by CMI when CDSs was employed as a clinical support team? During phase two, we monitored CMI to examine if CMI was moving either up or down. In addition and most importantly, we did daily evaluations of the study to ensure that the methodology was

followed as planned. For example, the hospitalist maintained 100% compliance to the use of EHRs for documentation and CDSs followed 100% of the hospitalist charts to ensure accurate inclusion of appropriate MCC and CC diagnoses.

PROPOSED PROJECT

The objective of the project was to evaluate the impact of EHRs implementation and CDSs clinical support teams on hospitalist documentation of MS-DRGs amongst an organization that places a high degree of merit on provider documentation to maintain quality patient care. The product of my doctoral work will be a manuscript to be submitted to the *Journal of Health and Medical Informatics*. I will carefully review the author guidelines for the journal (Appendix B) and work with my committee to submit a publishable manuscript describing the findings of the quality improvement study that evaluated the impact of EHRs with the addition of CDSs on hospitalist documentation of MS-DRGs as measured by CMI.

RESULTS

The study's purpose was to evaluate the impact of a newly adopted EHRs system and CDSs on provider documentation of MS-DRGs as measured by CMI. We noted no difference in race, gender, age, insurance status, providers, or CDSs participants between the pre and postimplementation phases.

The final data file consisted of a total of 3,536 patient records. There were a total of 1,712 records for the phase one analysis and a total of 1,824 records from phase two. Both phases of data collection used the same data format. Table 1 shows descriptive statistics for each phase. No difference was found in the mean between phase one, CMI 1.64, and phase two, CMI 1.68 ($p = .529$). The standard deviation range of variants also remained the same between phase one and phase two. A one-way ANOVA revealed, amongst the two phases, that there was no statistically significant difference in CMI, $F(1, 3534) = .397, p = .529$. Table 2 shows the results of the ANOVA between phases.

Subgroup analysis of the five chosen MS-DRGs (Table 3) yielded no difference in the mean between phase one and phase two with the exception of MS-DRGs (682) Acute Renal Failure with MCC; phase one yielded a CMI 1.64 and phase two yielded a CMI 1.80.

Power analysis and effect size were not performed at the beginning of the study because no previous studies were performed for comparison; thus, we were unable to acquire working data that would help with power analysis. However, a post hoc power analysis (Figure 1) and A Priori power analysis (Figure 2) were performed (Table 4). We calculated an observed power of .097 using a univariate, general linear model analysis on the current study (Table 5).

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics of CMI for Each Phase

CMI	Phase One	Phase Two	<i>p</i>
Mean	1.64	1.68	.45
Median	1.22	1.25	
Variance	2.42	2.51	
Standard Deviation	1.56	1.58	
Minimum	0.43	0.43	
Maximum	18.12	17.99	
Range	17.69	17.56	

Table 2

ANOVA of CMI by Phase

CMI	Sum of squares	<i>df</i>	Mean square	<i>F</i>	Sig.
Between groups	.980	1	.980	.397	.529
Within groups	8716.764	3534	2.467		
Total	8717.743	3535			

Table 3

CMI Mean Values for Each Phase by DRGs Codes

DRGs	Phase One CMI Mean	Phase Two CMI Mean
(682) Acute Renal Failure with MCC	1.64	1.80
(684) Acute Renal Failure without MCC	0.65	0.64
(870) Sepsis with Mechanical Ventilation greater than 96 hours	5.83	5.70
(871) Sepsis without Mechanical Ventilation for 96 hours or greater with MCC	1.91	1.90
(872) Sepsis without Mechanical Ventilation for 96 hours greater without MCC	1.14	1.18

Figure 1. Post hoc power analysis.

Figure 2. A Priori power analysis.

Table 4

Power Analysis Results

	Effect Size	Alpha Error Probability	Degrees of Freedom	Power	Mean Group 1	Mean Group 2
Post Hoc	0.02	0.05	3534	.097	1.65	1.68
A Priori	0.02	0.05	69,760 ^a	.800	1.65	1.68

^aEach group with 34,880.

Table 5

Univariate, General Linear Model With Observed Power

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	<i>df</i>	Mean Square	<i>F</i>	Sig.	Noncent. Parameter	Observed Power ^a
Corrected Model	.980 ^b	1	.980	.397	.529	.397	.097
Intercept	9748.533	1	9748.533	3952.306	.000	3952.306	1.000
Phase	.980	1	.980	.397	.529	.397	.097
Error	8716.764	3534	2.467				
Total	18482.265	3536					
Corrected Total	8717.743	3535					

^aComputed using alpha = 0.05.

^b $R^2 = 0.000$ (adjusted $R^2 = 0.000$).

DISCUSSION

Our findings suggest that the implementation of EHRs and CDSs did not show a statistically significant impact on CMI. Rather, the diligence of providers that document accurate and comprehensive MS-DRGs diagnosis with an appropriate addition of MCC and CC diagnoses guide CMI. We can accurately declare this association, as CMI is established by the observed number of MS-DRGs during a determined time period and the weight of the MS-DRGs, all of which are determined by clinical provider documentation without influence from any other variable.

The study was underpowered by a limited sample size. Post hoc power analysis revealed that a sample size of 69,758 would allow for better analysis. The time to acquire this sample size was unrealistic given the size of our hospital and the time given to complete the study. The main questions were answered given the restraints of the study sample size. The objective of the study was to ascertain if EHRs degraded our established high quality documentation of MS-DRGs diagnosis. We discovered that the implementation of EHRs did not significantly impact our documentation techniques. Practically, we propose that the addition of CDSs, as a clinical support group, actually countered any untoward documentation effects of the new EHRs system.

Furthermore, the effect size of the study is an important variable that should not be overlooked. Small changes in CMI reflect large reimbursement swings. The study revealed that implementation of EHRs and CDSs did not significantly impact CMI. Yet, an increase in CMI from 1.64 to 1.68, although not statistically significant, translated into a financial gain for the study time period of \$414,923. Also, based on the study findings, it is difficult to comment on the relevance of the small increase in CMI specific to our

study environment at our facility as our initial CMI is considerably higher compared to similar hospitals in our geographic region because of the outstanding level of our documentation at the start of the study. As documentation of MS-DRGs diagnosis with the addition of MCC and CC reach a maximum level, the capacity for improvement or increase in CMI diminishes. The limited capacity to improve documentation to a significant level given our small sample size may have contributed to not meeting statistical significance.

A poststudy review of CMI data in our geographic area comparing hospitals within a 40-mile radius that are similar in patient population served, size, services rendered, and blended rate yielded an average CMI for these institutions of 1.34. Calculating the financial impact of the difference, we used the findings for our postimplementation data ($N = 1,824$; blended rate = \$5,600; CMI = 1.68) and found that our institution's revenue related only to CMI was \$3,472,896 more compared to these other hospitals.

In 2007, J. A. Thomas and Associates analyzed 194,620 cases from multiple hospital centers that adopted the new MS-DRGs system to evaluate the revenue-generating power of MS-DRGs and CMI ("Hospitals With Clinical Documentation Improvement Program," 2008). The results indicated a powerful financial opportunity for hospitals. For example, for a hospital that has approximately 5,600 discharges per year with a CMI of 1.92 that increased by 0.1 to 2.02 increased monthly revenue to \$406,212, annual revenue increased to \$4,874,539, and 3-year revenue increased to \$14,623,616. The most important attributes of CMI is the representation of quality patient care. It has become increasingly clear that reporting of hospital quality statistics

to federal and public forums will be an important variable to the success of institutions, both financially and in reputation. Accurate and comprehensive documentation of MS-DRGs, MCC, and CC diagnoses reflects expected mortality of a hospital patient population. In contrast, inaccurate documentation will lower the expected mortality statistics, thereby increasing the expected/observed mortality ratio, consequently placing the institution at risk for penalties, investigation, and public stigma of poor care.

In comparison to similar hospitals in our geographic area with similar patient populations and resources, our institution carries a CMI that is substantially higher. This is explained by the general culture of the institution to educate providers to accurate and comprehensive documentation. Zalatimo et al. (2014), Spellberg et al. (2013), and Barnes et al. (2010) found that educational methods to improve provider documentation of MS-DRGs, MCC, and CC diagnosis improved CMI that ultimately increased institutional revenue and quality markers.

EHRs systems will become more advanced and engineered to enhance provider documentation when institutions move to understand the importance of comprehensive documentation and CMI as the measurement of provider documentation as tools for organizational success both in quality of care and financial health.

Study Limitations

Several study limitations exist for this study. The study was performed at a single hospital. The sample was extremely low with a post hoc power analysis of .097. The allowable time of the study was restricted to 1 year postimplementation that could not control for a postimplementation learning curve for the providers to learn the EHRs system. We did not have the resources or funding to control for the impact of CDSs and

EHRs to CMI separately. Hence, we were unable to evaluate the effect to CMI of each independent variable separately. The initial CMI was extremely high at the start of the study, which could have limited the significance of the study results.

Suggestions for Further Research

A Priori power analysis was performed to assist future studies. Our main recommendations for further studies include a larger sample size and control of EHRs and CDSs independently. The impact of MS-DRGs documentation with the appropriate addition of MCC and CC to CMI must start with a provider educational documentation program. Most importantly, strong leadership and a sound implementation strategy to foster buy-in from stakeholders are paramount. EHRs should be used as a tool to enhance documentation accuracy. Without foundational knowledge of comprehensive documentation, the impact to CMI will be negligible.

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APPENDIX A

TABLE OF EVIDENCE

Purpose Author/ Year	Design & Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Study Limitations, Authors' Conclusions, & Notes
(Babbott et al., 2014) Evaluate factors that produce stress and burnout in physicians that use electronic medical record (EMR). Provided solutions that may help with adjustment to EMR.	A latent class analysis identified clusters of physicians within clinics with low, medium and high EMR functions.	379 primary care physicians and 92 managers at 92 clinics from New York City and the upper Midwest participating in the 2001–5 Minimizing Error, Maximizing Outcome (MEMO) Study.	Assessed physician-reported stress, burnout, satisfaction, and intent to leave the practice, and predictors including time pressure during visits. Two-level regression model to estimate the mean response for each physician cluster to each outcome, adjusting for physician age, sex, specialty, work hours and years using the EMR. Effect sizes (ES) of these relationships were considered small (0.14), moderate (0.39), and large (0.61).	Compared to the low EMR cluster, physicians in the moderate EMR cluster reported more stress (ES 0.35, $p = 0.03$) and lower satisfaction (ES -0.45 , $p = 0.006$). Physicians in the high EMR cluster indicated lower satisfaction than low EMR cluster physicians (ES -0.39 , $p = 0.01$). Time pressure was associated with significantly more burnout, dissatisfaction and intent to leave only within the high EMR cluster.	Stress may rise for physicians with a moderate number of EMR functions. Time pressure was associated with poor physician outcomes mainly in the high EMR cluster. Work redesign may address these stressors.
(Barnes et al., 2010) To evaluate the impact to hospitals revenue of an educational.	Retrospective pre-post implementation.	Hospital trauma service. Sample not stated.	Trauma service characteristics, case mix index, reimbursement rate, payer distribution, hospital charges, cost, and payments were compared before and after standardization.	A 24% increase in the hospital's net income for trauma care, constituting \$1.45 million, was realized despite a 12% decrease in patient volume. Admission profitability increased by 42%. Collection rates and payer mix	An effective standardized documentation strategy for trauma care results in significant fiscal gains in hospital reimbursement.

Purpose Author/ Year	Design & Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Study Limitations, Authors' Conclusions, & Notes
.program to teach providers documentation techniques.				were unchanged. Increases in both injury severity score and case mix index were seen ($p <$.05) after implementation of the program. Length of stay was decreased significantly.	
(Didier et al., 2008) Expert opinion on lessons learned from implementation of quality documentation strategies.	Retrospective review Physician documentation Physician champion MS-DRGs documentation improvement.	Unknown.	Physician documentation Physician champion MS-DRGs documentation improvement.	Improvement of documentation and buy-in of physicians after engagement of a physician champion and implementation steps.	From the physician perspective, the following steps will help engage your medical staff in this initiative: 1. Explain the history of prospective payment. 2. Connect codes and quality report cards. 3. Teach your physicians communication skills. 4. Enlist a physician champion. Within the revenue cycle, the education of physicians for improved clinical documentation is the third step in a four-tier approach: 1. Set up an MS-DRGs financial impact study. 2. Establish a clinical documentation improvement/integrity team. 3. Focus your physician education efforts. 4. Monitor and trend revenue.
(Galanter et al., 2010)	Utilize an EMR system that	$N = 1,011$ alerts triggered	Measures: included alert validity, alert yield and	Alert validity alerts = 96% +/- 1%	Demonstrates that EMR driven CPOE entry system

Purpose Author/ Year	Design & Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Study Limitations, Authors' Conclusions, & Notes
To improve accuracy and completeness of the problem list = diagnosis to code for severity of illness.	incorporates a clinical decision support intervention that alerted the provider, while putting in orders electronically to add to or modify the problem list. Key variables: EMR system alerts (IV) and problem list (DV).	University of Illinois Hospital, 450 beds, using EMR system Millennium.	accuracy of problem list additions. Operationally: during an order entry series on the EMR, alerts would pop-up to advise that a problem/diagnosis should be added to the official problem list.	False positive rate 5% Lowest rate of problem accuracy was 80% for the ischemic stroke problem list. Alert yield (alert that fired that yielded an addition to the problem list 76% +/- 2%. Of the 74%-78% additions to the problem list 95% +/-1% were accurate additions as determined by an independent reviewer.	assist in maintenance of the problem list. Limited to order entry systems that are compatible with EMR system in institution. Complications still exist with compliance as the clinicians used the problem list alert system only 75% of the time. Table one outlines specific trigger alerts with ICD-9 diagnosis. Excellent visual.
(Jha et al., 2009) Researchers wanted to see what the level of adoption of EMR in U.S. hospitals. The importance of adoption of EMR systems in the United States is directly related to the U.S. health policy to move towards	Survey study appears cross-sectional 2 hypothesis Large hospitals would have higher prevalence of adoption of EMR than smaller hospitals. Teaching hospitals would have higher adoption than non-teaching hospitals and private hospitals would be higher than public hospitals. Key variables EMR	2,952 hospitals, 63.1% of all acute care general hospitals surveyed.	IOM developed a list of functionalities of an inpatient EMR. Modified Delphi process to reach a consensus on 24 functions of a comprehensive EMR and 8 functions to classify the EMR as basic. Survey tool validated by a large panel of multidisciplinary group. 32 clinical functionalities of EMR to establish if comprehensive or basic EMR system.	< 2% of U.S. hospitals surveyed have a comprehensive EMR. 8-12% have a basic EMR system Comparison to the characteristics of respondent and non-respondent hospitals found modest significant difference ($p < .05$) used logistic-regression model that included all characteristics. Explored bivariate relationships between sizes, U.S. census region, ownership, teaching status,	5 limitations were noted in the study. Nonresponse rate bias (63%). Focus of the study was on adoption of EMR, did not evaluate if the systems were effective and were used. Did not clarify if the systems were certified by a certified body. Because of the low level of adoption could not predict the progress to comprehensive EMR compared to basic EMR Did not evaluate if the users were satisfied with the EMR system. My notes: This study is

Purpose Author/ Year	Design & Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Study Limitations, Authors' Conclusions, & Notes
100% EMR as dictated by the American Recovery and Reinvestment Act of 2009.	adoption and clinical functionalities in electronic format.		Operational EMR adoption - key functionalities which divided into 2 groups basic or comprehensive. Clinical functionalities- included physician and nursing components.	urban vs. rural location. Multivariable model to calculate levels of adoption of EMR, adjusted according to hospital characteristics size, region etc. Logistic-regression models adjusting for characteristics found all to be significant except region.	important for my project to ascertain the impact of my project to hospitals that adopted EMR with certain functionalities that allow for improving diagnosis inclusion and variables to calculate severity of illness.
(Kumar & Thomas, 2011) Pilot study The purpose of the study hired a cardiologist to review current hospital coded charts for missed technical fee reimbursement due to poor dictation and/or lack of knowledge of the new MS-DRGs coding system. After evaluating the coded charts	Retrospective study Hypothesis: is that the cardiologist would be able to find a number of missed reimbursement opportunities through analysis. Missed MS-DRGs diagnosis And severity of illness using MCC and CC.	Sample size 5 randomly chosen major metropolitan hospital in Minneapolis, Minnesota.	Documented and coded 5 charts as listed. After found MCC and CC with new severity of illness weight, DRGs was transferred to MS-DRGs. MS-DRGs are measured by diagnosis, MCC and CC extracted from dictation, progress notes that are written from providers.	#1 DRGs 424.1 with MCC MS-DRGs 278.01 increased payment to hospital \$13,950. #2 MS-DRGs 414.01 with MCC and CC added increased payment \$4,446. #3 MS-DRGs 414.8 MCC changed to MS-DRGs 424.23 increased \$4971. #4MS-DRGs 88.56 included MCC increased payment \$12,992. #5MD-DRGs 410.71with MCC and change MS-DRGs to 486.00 increased payment to \$11407. Overall increase of only 5	After the review of these charts it was found that inadequate clinician documentation can decrease the hospitals income by millions of dollars. Author notes with today's EMR systems the alerts and triggers should make it easier for the clinician to document more accurately. Authors offer an 8-point instruction model for a quality improvement project for hospitals to undertake. Limitations: obvious low sample size; however, the impact of those 5 random charts showed a significant

Purpose Author/ Year	Design & Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Study Limitations, Authors' Conclusions, & Notes
evaluation of missed income was noted.				random charts reviewed increased payment to hospital by \$47,766.	impact. Also note the complications surrounding patient privacy of medical records to be a problem.
(Mendez et al., 2014) Classify the significance of CMI as it relates to severity of illness between public and private sectors.	Multivariate analysis. CMI data from public and private institutions.	Not mentioned. Setting, a large inner city tertiary hospital center.	CMI, MS-DRGs, major comorbidities, severity of illness.	CMI is solely dependent on provider documentation that populates MS-DRGs with and without MCC and CC which thereby increases severity of illness. Because private sector has money to invest in documentation education the CMI and severity of illness rates are higher compared to public institutions.	No mention of limitations. However, several exist that were not addressed. Although private institutions have money for documentation education programs, many do not understand or employ these programs. Authors did not address the fact that residents and interns document much more thoroughly as part of their program demands thereby increasing CMI and severity of illness at a higher rate than private sectors providers who are generally more interested in volume rather than the quality of their documentation. They also did not mention that tertiary hospitals conduct much higher weighted procedures that raise CMI substantially.
(Paterson et al., 2010) The aim or	Qualitative study using a conceptual model.	20 clinics used pre-visit surveys, key	Measured by 89 item transcription coding scheme based on the	Validated there tools with a success-failure odds ratio 69.75, used to corroborate	After the framework was implemented Canadians physicians started using

Purpose Author/ Year	Design & Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Study Limitations, Authors' Conclusions, & Notes
purpose of this study was to teach clinicians practical information for best practices and lessons learned regarding use of EMRs. Developed a conceptual framework as a common point of reference for the members of the research team.	<p>Research questions: "How are EMR's implemented?" "How are EMR used in clinical practice?" "How can EMR adoption be increased and sustained."</p> <p>2 stage EMR system and Use Assessment Survey used to tailor the interviews.</p>	<p>informant interviews and observations. Thematic analysis of data gathered to answer research questions.</p>	<p>research questions. 3,749 coded quotations from physician interviews for 20 EMR case studies.</p>	<p>their findings. Framework established greater shared understanding. 89 concept categories, 26 as useful for capturing data on the information incentives to be applied to the code. 3 most frequent used codes yielded 2 positive to negative quotes, access to data 102:27, quality of care 94:4, interoperability 32:66.</p>	<p>EMR in primary care to the point that no clinic was using paper-based charts. It brought together and enabled the clinician and health informatics professional to share common ground to succeed.</p> <p>Problems with external systems functioning; was a roadblock to successful implantation of the program.</p>
(Rosenstein et al., 2009) To show the financial impact of DRGs to MS-DRGs conversion and the importance of physician documentation in increasing the financial gain by	Data mapping design to assess and project individual hospital and aggregate results after conversion of 2006 MED PAR DRGs to MS-DRGs.	2006 MED PAR baseline period. DRGs data converted into new MS-DRGs classification from standard DRGs. 53 hospitals included in study 10 top positive and negative	<p>MS-DRGs-severity of illness of diagnosis by documented MCC and CC to increase weight.</p> <p>MCC-major comorbid states (i.e., systolic/diastolic HF, acute renal failure, malnutrition).</p> <p>CC-HTN, DM, chronic kidney disease stage iv or greater.</p>	<p>53 hospitals top 10 DRGs were converted to MS-DRGs. As an aggregate total of approximately 66,000 cases were involved in the conversion. The hospitals loss under the DRGs system for the top 10 DRGs was a loss of approximately \$10 million. After conversion to MS-DRGs with MCC and CC a \$12 million gain was seen.</p>	<p>Significant potential financial impact from the new MS-DRGs. MS-DRGs system account for the severity of illness. Patients with MCC and CC documented account for the positive financial positive impact, and those that don't have documented MCC and CC account for the loss. Positive results also reveal better quality outcomes in that the MCC and CC addition to the</p>

Purpose Author/ Year	Design & Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Study Limitations, Authors' Conclusions, & Notes
including MCC and CC to the diagnosis.		DRGs to MS- DRGs conversions evaluated.			diagnosis extend expected length of hospital stay. 9 steps to successful documentation strategies: education, guidelines, order sets and pathways, clinical champions, queries, CPOE, data, accountability, incentives.
(Spellberg et al., 2013) Evaluate the impact of an educational program to improve documentation.	Retrospective study pre-post implementation. Mortality rates, CMI, MCC, CC, MD- DRGs.	Large university based tertiary center. No sample size given.	Mortality rate, CMI, MCC, CC.	The median quarterly complication codes and major complication codes capture rate for inpatients on the internal medicine service was 42% before the intervention versus 48% after ($p = .003$). Observed mortality did not change but expected mortality increased, resulting in a 30% decline in median quarterly mortality index ($p = .001$). The median quarterly case mix index increased from 1.27 to 1.36 ($p = .004$).	Implementation of an internal medicine documentation curriculum improved accuracy in documenting diagnoses and comorbidities, resulting in improved capture of complication codes. Error in analysis: CMI coded as ordinal data when it is actually interval. Used Mann- Whitney U test inappropriately for CMI. Should have used ANOVA or t-test which would of not showed statistical significance. However, the theory and discussion is accurate.
(Spurgeon et al., 2011) Quality improvement	Retrospective study reviewed at 3 different time intervals; Pre-active- post.	Neurosurgery adult in-patient at University of Missouri Hospital.	DV: SOI and ROM rated on a 4 point scale (minor, moderate, major, extreme) scale levels set by DRGs (ICD-9)/Procedure weight	Chart Review intervention- 8 week period, 44.7% no response to query = no change in record, poor response rate. SOI/ROM = 1.40,1.43,1.56 (p	Despite expecting the SOI and ROM capture to increase during and after intervention the study could not statistically prove that the

Purpose Author/ Year	Design & Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Study Limitations, Authors' Conclusions, & Notes
project to promote improved provider documentation in order to more accurately represent ICD-9 coding and capture SOI and ROM which in turn leads to appropriate reimbursement to the hospital.	DV: SOI and ROM IV: Group in-service, progress note template, concurrent medical record coder review.	Randomly assigned $N = 1,009$. 329 patient's pre- intervention group, 306 patient concurrent during the intervention, 374 patients post- intervention. 300 patients per interval time period gave a power of 80% to detect differences in the mean scores of 0.25 units.	IV (group in-service)-30- minute group in-service on coding diagnosis and procedures and dynamics of SOI and ROM given to faculty and residents. IV (progress note template) developed by multidisciplinary group and approved for use. Used by all faculty and residents in neurosurgical unit after instruction on use was performed. IV (concurrent MRR coder) nurse reviewer, using strict tool designed by the group conducted concurrent review on active charts. Queries were sent out to the providers to change or add diagnosis.	$= .02, X^2$ Effect of age and sex on SOI/ROM = age differences were significant; however, the effect of age and sex on SOI/ROM was not significant. SOI ($p = .24$) ROM ($p = .48$) Effect of diagnosis: When adjusted for age and sex ($p =$.28), the primary diagnosis did not differ significantly between the pre-intervention and intervention time periods. ($p = .13$). When pre- intervention and intervention were combined there was a significance difference in primary diagnosis. ($p < .001$, Cochran-Mantel-Haenszel).	interventions increased capture of SOI/ROM. The failure to make a difference was not related to age, sex or primary diagnosis. Several factors could have occurred. The intervention fidelity could have corrected the response rates from providers. In addition validity and reliability of the tools had face validity however should be re-evaluated for reproducibility The interventions were appropriate as other studies, Grogan (2004) validated the progress note; however, rigor to adhere to the progress note template demanded provider compliance, unlike this study with poor (45%) response rate.
(Zalatimo et al., 2014) Educational program to increase accurate documentation of MS-DRGs.	Retrospective pre- post implementation of education program on documentation.	University tertiary center Sample size not mentioned.	Mortality, revenue, CMI, MCC, CC.	The median quarterly complication codes and major complication codes capture rate for inpatients on the internal medicine service was 42% before the intervention versus 48% after ($p = .003$). Observed mortality did not change but expected mortality	Thus, implementation of an internal medicine documentation curriculum improved accuracy in documenting diagnoses and comorbidities, resulting in improved capture of complication codes.

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Study Limitations, Authors' Conclusions, & Notes
				<p>increased, resulting in a 30% decline in median quarterly mortality index ($p = .001$).</p> <p>The median quarterly case mix index increased from 1.27 to 1.36 ($p = .004$).</p>	

APPENDIX B

AUTHOR GUIDELINES FOR *JOURNAL OF HEALTH & MEDICAL INFORMATICS*

Instructions for Authors

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Also, include current telephone and fax numbers, as well as postal and E-mail address of corresponding author to maintain communication.

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Manuscript title: The title should be limited to 25 words or less and should not contain abbreviations. The title should be a brief phrase describing the contents of the paper.

Author Information: Complete names and affiliation of all authors, including contact details of corresponding author (Telephone, Fax and E-mail address).

Abstract: The abstract should be informative and completely self-explanatory, briefly present the topic, state the scope of the experiments, indicate significant data, and point out major findings and conclusions. The abstract should summarize the manuscript content in 300 words or less. Standard nomenclature should be used and abbreviations should be

avoided. The preferable format should accommodate a description of the study background, methods, results and conclusion. Following the abstract, a list of keywords (3-10) and abbreviations should be included.

Text:

Introduction: The introduction should set the tone of the paper by providing a clear statement of the study, the relevant literature on the study subject and the proposed approach or solution. The introduction should be general enough to attract a reader's attention from a broad range of scientific disciplines.

Materials and Methods: This section should provide a complete overview of the design of the study. Detailed descriptions of materials or participants, comparisons, interventions and types of analysis should be mentioned. However, only new procedures should be described in detail; previously published procedures should be cited and important modifications of published procedures should be mentioned briefly. Capitalize trade names and include the manufacturer's name and address.

Results: The results section should provide complete details of the experiment that are required to support the conclusion of the study. The results should be written in the past tense when describing findings in the authors' experiments. Previously published findings should be written in the present tense. Results and discussion may be combined or in a separate section. Speculation and detailed interpretation of data should not be included in the results but should be put into the discussion section.

Acknowledgement: This section includes acknowledgment of people, grant details, funds, etc.

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1. Laemmli UK (1970) Cleavage of structural proteins during the assembly of the head of bacteriophage T4. *Nature* 227: 680-685.
2. Brusic V, Rudy G, Honeyman G, Hammer J, Harrison L (1998) Prediction of MHC class II- binding peptides using an evolutionary algorithm and artificial neural network. *Bioinformatics* 14: 121-130.
3. Doroshenko V, Airich L, Vitushkina M, Kolokolova A, Livshits V, et al. (2007) YddG from *Escherichia coli* promotes export of aromatic amino acids. *FEMS Microbiol Lett* 275: 312-318.

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1. http://eutils.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/entrez/query/static/eutils_help.html

Books:

1. Baggot JD (1999) Principles of drug disposition in domestic animals: The basis of Veterinary Clinical Pharmacology. (1stedn), W.B. Saunders Company, Philadelphia, London, Toronto.
2. Zhang Z (2006) Bioinformatics tools for differential analysis of proteomic expression profiling data from clinical samples. Taylor & Francis CRC Press.

Conferences:

1. Hofmann T (1999) The Cluster-Abstraction Model: unsupervised learning of topic hierarchies from text data. Proceedings of the International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence.

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